
Leveraging Deep Learning and Neural Networks for Emotions recognition in EEG signals

Lorenzo Sciarretta

Department of Computer Science,
Politecnico di Milano,
Milan, Italy.

lorenzo.sciarretta@mail.polimi.it

*

Abstract

Emotion recognition through EEG signal analysis is an essential issue in artificial intelligence, offering significant potential in emotional health care, human-computer interaction, and multimedia content recommendation. While traditional EEG analysis provides foundational brain activity insights, our research investigates advanced computational models that improve the accuracy and depth of emotion and cognitive state detection. By integrating sophisticated convolutional neural networks and innovative machine learning strategies, we aim to achieve high precision in EEG signal monitoring and interpretation. Our work compares the latest deep learning techniques using EBNeuro's high-end EEG research technology with a focus on applications in mental health diagnostics, interactive computing, and adaptive environments. A critical challenge we address is the adaptation of EEG data into CNN-compatible formats, a step crucial for the effective application of DL methodologies.

*We extend our sincere gratitude to the EBNeuro s.p.a. R&D team for their support and assistance throughout the duration of this work.